

IMPROVEMENT OF LEGAL MEASURES TO COMBAT THE DISSEMINATION OF ANTI-SOCIAL BEHAVIOR AMONG YOUTH

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Abstract. The article analyzes national and foreign legislation, theoretical opinions of legal scholars, and judicial and investigative practice related to combating the spread of antisocial behavior among youth. Based on the research findings, proposals and recommendations have been developed to prevent the spread of antisocial behavior among youth, particularly to improve responsibility for involving a person in antisocial behavior.

Keywords: youth, juvenile, child, antisocial, illegal, behavior, involvement, behavior, violation of rights, crime.

It is known that every person, starting from childhood, grows up under the influence of the social environment, resulting in the formation of a certain character. If a child grows up in an antisocial environment or under its influence, their involvement in antisocial behavior or committing an offense is easier than that of their other peers. According to statistical data, in 2021, the proportion of young people in the total number of crimes committed was 38% (including: 19.3% aged 25-30, 15.5% aged 18-24, 2.7% aged 16-17, 2.7% aged 13-15). These figures indicate that today the issue of combating the spread of antisocial behavior among young people is not only relevant, but also the need to improve legal measures to combat the spread of antisocial behavior in society.

In Uzbekistan, every child has the right to health protection, and the state, through the introduction of special restrictions and the implementation of special preventive programs, takes the necessary measures to protect the child from alcohol dependence, smoking, the use of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and other substances that affect intellectual and volitional activity. Currently, the republic is implementing numerous measures aimed at preventing the spread of antisocial behavior among youth.

At the same time, research shows that as a result of the weakening of legal and educational work among minors, the unsatisfactory solution of employment and other problems, as well as excessive oversight functions, there is an increase in the number of cases of committing offenses and crimes by many young people, drug addiction and alcoholism, religious fanaticism or exposure to various harmful currents, groups. In some cases, the spread of antisocial behavior among young people, the commission of crimes by them, is also caused by the negative influence of adults, in particular, parents, close relatives and other persons, and sometimes by the late notification of the antisocial behavior of a minor, the commission of a crime, or the failure to provide information to law enforcement agencies.

For example, according to the results of the socio-psychological survey "Study of the Commitment of Antisocial Behavior by Minors as a Result of Voluntary or Other Influences," 56.48% of antisocial behavior was committed by children and adolescents at their own discretion, 10.64% as a result of the influence of peers or other influences, 8.24% as a result of

the influence of adults, 4.39% as a result of the influence of parents and relatives, and 11.84% as a result of the influence of previously convicted.

It should be noted that young people are more susceptible to external influences. According to experts, in some cases, as a result of not always achieving goals in life, young people experience a "infant" mood (feeling helpless, need help).

Some researchers note that "the social environment plays a decisive role in the formation of the individual, including the criminal." In our view, although a person's behavior is the cause of a crime, this behavior is shaped by the influence of social institutions. S.B. Khodzhakulov notes that the commission of any crime is known to arise as a result of the interaction of the spiritual and psychological state (unsocial behavior) formed in a person with a certain social environment at the time of the crime. Agreeing with this opinion, it should be noted that in some cases, crimes are committed by individuals, especially minors, as a result of the physical or psychological influence of others.

In the conducted research, most parents or their substitutes stated that their minor children committed crimes as a result of not knowing how to properly raise their children, while some did not think about proper upbringing at all.

In this regard, let's pay attention to the lexical meaning of the terms "unusual social behavior" and "unusual social behavior." In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the word "файри" is given definitions such as "other, other; external" or a noun word used to form the opposite of the word added to it, and the word "ижтимоий" is given definitions such as "belonging to the life of man and society," "connected with society, belonging to society, society."

Therefore, the word "anti-social" is used in the sense of "anti-society." In this dictionary, the word "attitude" is defined as "walking, behavior," the word "behavior" is defined as "a complex of human behavior and spiritual characteristics; the verb, character," "attitude that has become habitual and repeated to a person; habit, behavior," and "behavior" is defined as a combination of the words "behavior" and "behavior," that is, "character." It can be seen that the words "anti-social" are used in relation to the behavior prohibited by administrative law, and "illegal" in relation to the act prohibited by criminal law.

For example, an illegal, guilt-ridden (intentional or negligent) act or omission that violates the rights and freedoms of individuals, citizens, property, state and public order, the natural environment, for which administrative responsibility is provided, is considered an "administrative offense," a socially dangerous act prohibited by the Criminal Code (acting or omission) is considered a "crime."

Article 35 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan enshrines the rule that "even if the act officially contains the signs provided for in this Code, but it is socially dangerous, illegal or culpable, it is considered circumstances that exclude the criminality of the act."

While national legislation defines antisocial behavior as "a way of life, action or inaction of a person that violates accepted norms and rules of conduct in society," in some countries it is defined as "a behavior or inaction of a person that does not cause administrative or criminal liability, does not constitute a violation of generally accepted norms of conduct and morality, the rights and legitimate interests of other persons" or "a violation of the rights of a person, an act or inaction that does not constitute an administrative or criminal liability."

In our opinion, it is not the way of life of a person, but only the act (action or inaction) they perform that can have an antisocial character. An act of a person that entails administrative or criminal liability shall be considered "unlawful behavior," and actions that violate generally accepted moral and ethical norms, the rights and legitimate interests of other persons, which do not cause such liability, shall be considered "unlawful behavior." If a person commits an administrative offense or a crime, his actions shall be recognized as illegal. Based on this, we consider it expedient to make appropriate amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses."

Similar definitions of the term "unsocial behavior" can be seen in national and foreign legislation on the prevention of uncontrollability and violations of rights among minors. For example, according to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, antisocial behavior is behavior of a minor, expressed in the regular consumption of alcoholic beverages, narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances or other substances affecting intellectual activity, prostitution, begging, as well as other actions that violate the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of other citizens.

In the legislation of the Russian Federation, non-social actions are the actions of minors, expressed in the regular use of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances or other substances affecting intellectual activity, alcohol and alcohol-containing products, prostitution, prostitution, begging, as well as the actions of persons who do not have the right to comply with the requirements of the legislation of the Republic of Tajikistan on the grounds of non-public rights and interests of minors, as well as the rights of persons who do not have the right to comply with the requirements of It can be seen that deviance is not evaluated as an antisocial behavior in the legislation of Uzbekistan. However, the "Regulations on the Criteria for Determining the Age Classification of Information Products and the Procedure for Their Expertise" stipulates that anti-public actions, including the consumption of alcohol and alcohol-containing products, beer and beverages based on it, participation in gambling and begging, must be understood.

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